
FOREST CONSERVATION POLICY: THE ROLE OF STATE FORESTRY DEPARTMENT IN OYO STATE.

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ABSTRACT

Forests provide diverse services and will continue to remain an integral part of rural livelihoods. Demand for forest products, especially timber became insatiably high as results of increasing human population pressure and economic growth. This led to unregulated forest exploitation, thus resulting in degradation of the resources in the country. Lack of forest management plan, primitive silvicultural operation, and under-utilization of resources and high rate of illegal logging in the forest plantation resulted in alarming failure of forest plantation to meet the current demand for both timber and non – timber forest products. Forest policies have to be tailored in a way that the primary focus is on maintaining ecosystem integrity. In Nigeria constitution Oyo State is a typical example of where timber exploitation has been taking place without adequate regeneration despite regular payment of regeneration fees. The study was conducted in Onigambari which is located in Oluyole Local Government Area. Simple descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentages were used to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Chi-square analysis was also used to analyze the relationship between the activities of forest users and the roles of State Department of Forestry in Oyo State. This paper focuses on forest conservation policy with a view to examine activities of forest users and the role of State Forestry department under the auspices of Ministry of Agriculture in Oyo State, Nigeria. Illegal activities being perpetrated by various forest users has been found detrimental to the forest reserves. Poaching (e.g. hunting of animals, harvesting of forest resources, and mismanagement of eco – system among others) has been identified as the major threat such that little or no other form of illegal activity can be carried out in the forest reserves except through poaching. These illegal activities have been however checked and reduced to manageable level by the forest law enforcement agents in the state under the auspices of Ministry of Agriculture. Thus, the culprits are subjected to varying degrees of penalty and punishment

KEYWORDS: Forest Conservation Policy, Forestry Department, Poaching, Sustainable Forest Management.

INTRODUCTION

Forestry is a provincial subject with planning, execution and implementation of forest, watershed and range improvement programs vested in provincial forest departments. Forestry development began in Nigeria in 1889 with emphasis on forest reservation and regulated timber exploitation (Geomatics, 1997). Forests provide diverse services and will continue to remain an integral part of rural livelihoods. In 1980's, demand for forest products, especially timber became insatiably high as a results of increasing human population pressure and economic growth. This led to unregulated forest exploitation, thus resulting in degradation of the resources in the country. Currently, forestry sector is confronted with many challenges: massive degradation of watersheds, deforestation, encroachments, conversion of forests to non-forestry uses, overuse of rangelands, habitat and biodiversity loss, desertification, climate change, prolonged droughts, environmental pollution, heavy dependence of rural population on biomass energy, complex land tenure, weak forestry institutions, ineffective enforcement of law and lack of inter-sectoral coordination.

In developing countries including Nigeria, people's livelihoods are dependent on land and forest resources therefore, proper governance and management of these resources are recognized as essential components of Poverty Alleviation Programme which is in the formulation stage may assist the potential of forests in poverty alleviation and strongly advocates mainstreaming of sectoral policies to address the problems of forest and land degradation through sustainable land management practices. FORMECU (1994) reported that the average

annual rate of deforestation in Nigeria between 1980 and 1990 was 3.5% while Enaboret *et al.* (1986) argued that land clearance for cropping by subsistence farmers in shifting cultivation account for about 80% of the deforestation of Nigeria. Nwoboshi (1986) reported that in 1876 it was estimated that 60 million hectares of the total land area of Nigeria was forested while in 1985, this figure declined to about 9.4 million hectares. Anadu and Green observed that Nigeria has lost more than 90% of its primary moist lowland forest. Presently Nigeria has 15% forest cover (FAO, 2004).

It has been estimated that only about 360,000 km² (25.6%) of Nigeria land mass is under forest and woodland shrubs cover (FAO, 2003). In an attempt to preclude total depletion of forest resources, the Federal Government of Nigeria has geared effort towards increasing 10% (91,000 km²) of the total land area under forest reserve to 20% towards meeting the FAO specification of 25% in the future. In 1990's, the area of industrial forest plantation in Nigeria was about 160,000 ha while the area of environmental plantation was 48,000 ha (Oyebo and Okirigbo, 1999).

Lack of forest management plan, primitive silvicultural operation, and under-utilization of resources and high rate of illegal logging in the forest plantation resulted in alarming failure of forest plantation to meet the current demand for both timber and non – timber forest products (F.D.F, 1998).

Furthermore, large scale encroachments and allocation of forest lands to non-forestry uses continued due to lack of political will, ineffective implementation of forest policies and legislation. Prescriptions of the management plans were not strictly followed and forest departments' functioning under weak political governments could not achieve any success in adopting principles of Sustainable Forest Management. A recent survey shows that forest policies in most developing countries have not emerged as a result of any concern, new vision, research or monitoring based feed-back from previous policies but mostly due to change in the political governments. While focus of most forest policies during twentieth century remained on commercial harvesting to generate revenue, apathy to maintain vigor, ecosystem services and functions of the natural forests prevailed during all these years leading to threshold levels of forest degradation. As such forest policies announced by the Federal Government could not transform principles of forest conservation/sustainable forest management on ground and yielded no significant change in extending forest resource base.

Forest policies have to be tailored in a way that the primary focus is on maintaining ecosystem integrity, the benefits and services derived from the forests have to be linked with the livelihoods of all the stakeholders especially the effective users living in the vicinity of forests.

Therefore, issues of forest degradation, sustainable livelihoods and poverty alleviation would need to be mainstreamed in sectoral policies related to forests and rural development, or else the realization forest conservation will remain a myth. This paper focuses on forest conservation policy with a view to examining activities of forest users and the role of State Forestry department under the auspices of Ministry of Agriculture in Oyo State, Nigeria.

FOREST CONSERVATION POLICY

In Nigeria constitution, Forestry is a state subject that means; the various state governments in the country own and manage their forest estates. This makes it possible for the state to side track well spelt-out forest conservation policy objectives. Oyo state is typical example of where timber exploitation has been taking place without adequate regeneration despite regular payment of regeneration fees. This is because the government in such state that is rich in timber exploits the elements of forestry through the use of veto powers (Adeyoju, 1996). Garrity and Lai, (2000) noted that government policies in some countries actively encourage sedentary agriculture in the plantation/Forest. In most of the plantations and reserves, permanent agriculture crops as well as arable crops have encroached the forest estates. For instance oil palm and cocoa plantation have taken over the considerable proportion of Forest estates. It accounts for allocating of forests for harvesting and abandonment of forest land for other users outside permanent vegetation cover.

Timber investment organization is faced with many uncertainties. The forest estate in Nigeria is currently 10% of the land area, which is far less than the original recommended 25%. In addition the country has witnessed rapid population increase as well as economic growth which resulted in further degradation of the forest estate. It is for this reason that Oseni and Umeh, (1988) opined that the forest policy needs revision in order to arrest

the ugly trend. The forest policy in this country has centered on the frame work developed since pre-independence which focused mainly on forest exploitation (Papka, 1999). This accounts for reservation and/ or plantation establishment in Nigeria. Onigambari forest reserve in Oyo state was among early forest reserves in the country. The extent of plantation forest to be raised annually is one of the objectives of forest policy (Aladejana, 1971). It is most unfortunate that little attention is given to the needs of the immediate communities that depend on the forest prior to plantation establishment. Decision making institution focused on utilization and management of forest resources should be based on the knowledge of the community (Field – Juma, 1998). This should be done within the framework of their work views, in other words, in accordance with their ethics, norms and beliefs. Policies are formulated to provide a frame work to address the management and development of forestlands, market and price policies as well as the ones relating to private Forestry and researches in Forestry. According to 2006 national forest policy, the overall objectives of forest policy are to prevent further deforestation and to recreate forest cover, either for productive or for protective purposes on already deforested fragile land. Specifically, the National Agricultural Policy of 1988 in which the Forestry Policy is subsumed provides for:

- Consolidation and expansion of the forest estate in Nigeria and its management for sustained yield.
- Regeneration of the forests at rates higher than exploitation.
- Conservation and protection of the environment viz: Forest, soil, water, flora, fauna and the protection of the forest resources from fires, cattle grazers and illegal encroachment.
- Development of Forestry industry through the harvesting and utilization of timber, its derivatives and the reduction of wastes.
- Wildlife conservation, management and development through the creation and effective management of national parks, game reserves, tourist and recreational facilities, etc.

These policy objectives have been well enunciated and appear well meant and the means for achieving them have been well articulated. Indeed one of the strategies for achieving the consolidation and expansion of the forest estate was the expansion of the forest estate from 10% to 20%. This so far has remained elusive. For the above policy or objectives to be achieved, significant legal and policy changes are needed. The needs for national policy can never be overemphasized, in fact energies and resources of the nation are being devoted to achieve these social goals (Sehgah, 1992). Therefore, it becomes imperative to adopt policy that secures the survival of the people as the national priority (de-montalembert, 1999).

METHODOLOGY.

Study Area.

The study was conducted at Onigambari forest reserve which is located in Oluyole Local Government Area. It lies between latitude $7^{\circ} 22'$ and $9^{\circ} 17'$ North; and longitude $1^{\circ} 2'$ and $2^{\circ} 44'$ East and Olokemeji forest reserve which is situated in Ibarapa Local Government Area both in Oyo-State, Nigeria. The two identifiable seasons are the rainy season which begins from late March to October and dry season stretching from November to early March. The mean annual temperature varies between 21.1°C and 31.1°C . The annual rainfall is within the range of 800mm in the derived eco-zone to 1500mm in the rainforest belt. The rainfall is bimodal with its peak in July and September (Faleyimu and Agbeja, 2004).

Method of Data Collection:

A reconnaissance survey visit was conducted at Onigambari Forest Reserve and Olokemeji Forest Reserve and 60 structured questionnaires were administered and retrieved. Hence, 30 structured questionnaires were distributed in each forest reserves for primary data to elicit information concerning the perception of forest conservation and policy among the forest guards in the Forest reserve.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentages were used to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Chi-square analysis was also used to analyse the relationship between the activities of forest users and the roles of State Department of Forestry in Oyo State.

Table 1: Forest Reserves in Oyo State

Forest Reserves	Part Converted to Plantation	Zones/ L.G.A
(Ha)	(Ha)	
Opara	3,544	Saki
Baasi	1,144	Saki
Okoo-Iroo	2,299	Ogbomosho (Ogo Oluwa)
Olaseinde	686	Oyo (Iseyin)
Gambari	11,437	Ibadan (Oluyole)
Olokemeji	75.11	Ibadan (Ibarapa)
Igangan	39,627	Ibadan (Ibarapa)
Ijaiye	28,491	Ibadan (Akinyele)
Oso	3,074	Ibadan (Akinyele)
Lanlate	7,507	Ibadan (Ibarapa)

Source: State Department of Forestry (2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Socio – Economic Characteristics of Respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
GENDER		
Male	57	95.0
Female	3	5.0
Total	60	100.0
AGE		
<30	12	20.0
30 - 39	21	35.0
40 - 49	12	20.0
> 50	15	25.0
Total	60	100.0
MARITALSTATUS		
Single	12	20.0
Married	45	75.0
Divorced	3	5.0
Total	60	100.0
RELIG ION		
Christianity	42	70.0
Islam	18	30.0
Total	60	100.0
YEAR OF EXPERIENCE		
< 10	9	15.0
11 - 15	21	35.0
16 - 20	18	30.0
> 20	12	20.0
Total	60	100.0
EDUCATIONAL STATUS		
Primary	6	10.0
Secondary	6	10.0
Vocational	18	30.0
Tertiary	3	50.0
Total	60	100.0

Field Survey 2011

Table 1 showed different forest reserves and their respective land areas converted to plantation in Oyo State. The total land area available for forest reservation amounts to 97,884.11 km² while the total landed area converted into forest plantation is 8,496.44km² representing 8.68% of the total forest area. This therefore revealed that 89,387.67km² amounting to (91.32%) were left unprotected. This however implied that there is a huge inefficiencies on the part of State Department of Forestry and other forestry related agencies and parastatals to have left such large expanse of forested land area unguarded and unprotected.

DISCUSSION

Table 2 showed that 95.0 percent of the respondents in the study area were male while female accounted for 5.0 percent of the respondents. This indicated that male were pre- dominant in various forestry activities and decision policy making within the study area. The study also showed that age group of respondents (30-39 years) has the highest percentage of 35.0 percent and the age group of less than 30 years and 40 – 49 years has the same percentage of 20.0 percent. This therefore indicated that middle age dominated those that involved in forest conservation policy and enforcement in the study area.

The study revealed that 75.0 percent of the respondents were married while single accounted for 20.0 percent of the respondents. It indicated that most married people were actively engaged in different roles of ensuring strict compliance of forest conservation policies such as forest protection, log control, forest regeneration, forest management and extension and administering necessary penalty and punishment to the trespassers in the study area.

The study showed that forest enforcement agents cut across the religion faith in the study area with Christianity and Islam having predominant percentage of 70.0 and 30.0 percent respectively. This indicated that religion is not a barrier among the respondents within the study area.

The study showed that 15.0 percent of the respondents fell below 10 years of experience while respondents with 11-15 years of experience has the highest percentage of 35.0. The study also showed that 30.0 and 20.0 percent of the respondents accounted for 16-20 years of experience and above 20 years of experience respectively This indicated that the forest officers in the study area can perform well because experience is an important factor that shows the performance and efficiency of the respondents in discharging their responsibilities in relation to forest conservation policy.

The study revealed that 10.0 percent of the respondents had primary and secondary school education respectively. 30.0 percent of the respondents interviewed were not educated (had vocational training) while tertiary education accounted for 50.0 percent of the respondents. This showed that half of the respondents are of high cadre with the minimum qualification of Ordinary National Diploma (OND) certificate.

Table 3: Chi-Square Analysis between Activities of Forest Users and the Role of State Forestry Department in Forest Conservation and Policy.

	Calculated X ²	Tabulated X ²	Df	Decision	Level of significance (p)
Poaching	33.600 ^c	7.82	3	S	0.05
Farming	29.400 ^b	7.82	3	S	0.05
Illegal felling	29.400 ^b	3.84	1	S	0.05
Punishment	21.600 ^b	3.84	1	S	0.05
Role of Forestry Department	63.000 ^a	9.49	4	S	0.05

Source: Survey Data 2011

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 25.0.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 20.0.

Df - Degree of freedom, P =0.05

Poaching

Table 3 showed that there is a significant relationship between poaching in the forest reserve under study and the role being played by the forest enforcement agents in the forest department in ensuring implementation of forest conservation policies. According to Kalu *et al.*, 2010, poaching has been identified among different threats to forest conservation and it is capable of altering the original state of the forest due to activities like harvesting of the forest resources and disturbing the eco – system among others.

Farming Activities

From the result of the finding, it is revealed that there is also a significant relationship between the farming activities and the role of the forest enforcement agents in the forest department in ensuring implementation of forest policies. Expansions of agricultural activities lead to exploitation of forest products. Lands are prepared through various methods such as bush burning, uncontrolled grazing, and illegal logging among others. This corroborates the view expressed by Tivy,(1996) that fire is one of the principal threats to forest because it destroys forest canopy and opens up for other forms of vegetation especially farming.

Illegal felling

The study also showed that there is a significant relationship between illegal felling and the role of the forest enforcement agents in the forest department. The study agrees with FAO (2001) which observed that Nigeria forest are increasingly at risk as a result of illegal felling .According to Kalu *et al* (2010), over 500 hectares of forest land in Edo State are destroyed yearly. Forest officers admits that illegal felling occurs almost all over the country both in forest reserves and in unreserved forest areas which has adverse effects on the conservation efforts on forest reserves

Punishment and the Role of State Forest Department

The result of the analysis on the punishment and the role of state forest department indicated that the punishment meted out to the trespassers is significant ($\chi^2=21.600^b$, $P=0.05$) ranking imprisonment, payment of fine, impoundment of operational tools in decreasing order. As shown in Table 2, the roles of state forest department ($\chi^2=63.000^a$, $P=0.05$) were significant and depended on forest protection, log control, regeneration, forest management and extension. Hence, the work of forest enforcement agents in the state is very imperative to the forest conservation policy.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Illegal activities being perpetrated by various forest users have been found detrimental to the forest reserves. Poaching (e.g. hunting of animals, harvesting of forest resources, and mismanagement of eco – system among others) has been identified as the major threat such that little or no other form of illegal activity can be carried out in the forest reserves except through poaching. Encroachments and allocation of forest lands to non-forestry uses is on the increase due to ineffective implementation of forest policies and legislation. These illegal activities have been however checked and reduced to manageable level by the forest law enforcement agents in the state under the auspices of ministry of agriculture. Thus, the culprits are subjected to varying degrees of penalty and punishment.

Arising from above, there is need for reorientation and enlightenment of the populace on the existing laws and policies guiding the forest reserves in order to ensure their conservation and sustainability and largely to maintain a balance eco – system. Also, there is need for proper training and empowerment of the forest law enforcement agents (forest guards) by the government in order to improve on their performances in implementing forest conservation policies within the forest reserves.

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